

Preventive measures to limit the spread of *Trioza erytreae* (Del Guercio) (Hemiptera: Triozidae) in mainland Europe

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Abstract

Trioza erytreae (Del Guercio) (Hemiptera: Triozidae) vectors the most important citrus disease, namely huanglongbing (HLB) or citrus greening. This vector has been recently found on the European mainland in the north-western region of the Iberian Peninsula (Spain and Portugal), although HLB has not yet been detected in Europe. Thus, preventing the spread of the vector is currently an urgent priority. Here, we show two prevention methods to avoid the spread of this psyllid from areas where it is present to psyllid-free areas. Our results showed that two types of anti-insect mesh with a pore size of $0.4 \times 0.77 \text{ mm}^2$ and $0.27 \times 0.77 \text{ mm}^2$ were effective in excluding *T. erytreae* in two field experiments. These results have direct implications in the nursery plant production system, which should adopt meshes with pore sizes small enough to guarantee the exclusion of *T. erytreae*. Additionally, we evaluated the longevity of *T. erytreae* on fruit to understand the risk of dispersion of the psyllid with unprocessed fruit movement between infested and non-infested areas. The longevity of *T. erytreae* on mandarin and lemon fruit under winter conditions (13.8°C and 85.4% of relative humidity) was 11 days for both fruits. We anticipate that our results could help enhance the preventive measures in citrus fruit areas without a presence of *T. erytreae*.

KEYWORDS

anti-insect meshes, citrus nursery, citrus transportation, HLB, pest management, quarantine measures

1 | INTRODUCTION

Trioza erytreae (Del Guercio) (Hemiptera: Triozidae) is the most recent key citrus pest introduced to the European mainland. This psyllid transmits *Candidatus Liberibacter africanus* (Claf), the bacterial agent of the most threatening disease for Mediterranean citrus, huanglongbing (HLB), or greening (Bové, 2006). *Trioza erytreae* was firstly detected in the north-west regions of Spain in 2014 (Pérez-Otero, Mansilla, & del Estal, 2015). Since then, this psyllid

pest has spread towards the southwest of the Portuguese coast, reaching Lisbon Province (DGAV, 2019). Fortunately, to date, *T. erytreae* has not reached the main citrus-producing areas, and HLB has been detected nowhere in Europe (Cocuzza et al., 2017; Pérez-Otero et al., 2015; Siverio et al., 2017). The Mediterranean region is the largest exporting and importing area in the world, with 8,842.5 tons of citrus exported and 2,065.3 thousand tons of citrus imported annually (FAO, 2019). This poses a severe risk for the spread of HLB vectors, which in turn pave the way for future HLB range

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expansions (Badaracco, Redes, Preussler, & Agostini, 2017; CDFA, 2019; Grafton-Cardwell, Stelinski, & Stansly, 2013; Manjunath, Halbert, Ramadugu, Webb, & Lee, 2008).

Trioza erytreae development ranges from 28 to 48 days (Catling, 1973; van Der Mewre, 1923; Moran & Blowers, 1967), with at least 6–8 generations throughout the year on citrus (Catling, 1972, 1978; Tamesse & Messi, 2004). Therefore, large areas can be colonized in a relatively short time, indicating that this psyllid moves from infested to uninfested plants, probably looking for new feeding and oviposition sites (Samways and Manicom, 1983). Indeed, the availability of young flushes has a strong effect on *T. erytreae* biology (Green & Catling, 1971; van der Mewre, 1923; Tamesse & Messi, 2004). Females oviposit eggs along the margins of young and tender leaves (Annecke & Cilliers, 1963; Moran & Buchan, 1975). Nymphal feeding activity produces a characteristic and noticeable pit gall protruding on the upper surface of leaves; it is the unequivocal symptom of the infestation of this species in citrus (Cocuzza et al., 2017). The pit gall increases in size with nymphal growth (van den Berg, Deacon, & Thomas, 1991), and the same nymph remains fixed in the same gall until adulthood is reached after passing through five nymphal instars (Cocuzza et al., 2017). As in other citrus-cultivating regions in the past, *T. erytreae* eradication failed in northern Spain and north-western Portugal (Cocuzza et al., 2017). Therefore, prevention and containment of the vector need to be implemented urgently to avoid the entrance of the vector into the main citrus-producing areas of Europe. The exotic parasitoid *Tamarixia dryi* (Waterson) (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) was introduced after host-specificity tests to reduce the spread of *T. erytreae* in the north-west regions of Spain (Pérez-Rodríguez et al., 2019; Urbaneja-Bernat et al., 2019). This specific wasp was released in northern Spain and north-western Portugal in the fall of 2019 as a part of a classical biological control programme. The classical biological control of *T. erytreae* with *T. dryi* became a successful solution to control this psyllid in citrus in Reunion Island (Aubert & Quilici, 1984; Pérez-Rodríguez et al., 2019). However, there are still no results from its establishment in mainland Europe. To augment this biological control strategy, additional methods need to be implemented urgently to reduce the spread of the vector in mainland Europe.

Surveillance in places near psyllid infested areas must be augmented to prevent or delay the entry of *T. erytreae* as long as possible in citrus regions. Among the strategies to prevent the spread of the vector, the use of anti-insect meshes in citrus nurseries in infested areas should be mandatory along with the adopted quarantine measures. Unfortunately, to date, little is known about the effectiveness of anti-insect mesh as a method to protect citrus from the new invasive pest *T. erytreae*. The first aim of this study was to evaluate five different commercial anti-insect meshes to increase the protection of citrus and avoid the spread of this psyllid, especially in citrus-growing nurseries.

In Florida, Halbert et al. (2010) demonstrated that both the vector *Diaphorina citri* Kuwayama (Hemiptera: Liviidae) and the bacterial agent, *Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus* (Clas) could be transported in long-distance movement on unprocessed fruit. It is known that

T. erytreae nymphs and adults prefer tender plant tissue (Moran, 1968), and *T. erytreae* adults can survive for 2–3 months on mature leaves when tender shoots are not available (Catling, 1972; Catling & Annecke, 1968). However, little is known about the survival of this psyllid on citrus fruit. For this reason, the second aim of this study was to evaluate the longevity of *T. erytreae* adults on lemon and mandarin fruit under winter and summer conditions. These results could improve quarantine measures concerning the movement of citrus fruit (import/export) from areas with *T. erytreae* presence to pest-free citrus areas.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Plants and insect rearing

Two-year-old pesticide-free lemon plants were used to rear *T. erytreae* at the Instituto Canario de Investigaciones Agrarias (ICIA) (28°31'29" N 16°22'12" W) located in Tenerife, Spain, where this psyllid has been present since 2002 (Pérez-Padrón & Carnero, 2002). Plants were kept in a greenhouse at 23 ± 5 °C, 70 ± 15% of RH, watered twice per week and fertilized once per week using a modified Hoagland's solution. Young trees were pruned to obtain homogeneous young flush. Trees were infested with adult psyllids when the oldest leaves of the new flush measured about 4 cm. For the establishment of the colony, ~200 *T. erytreae* adults were collected from pesticide-free lemon trees located in Tenerife province (Canary Islands, Spain). To obtain newly emerged individuals, tender apical lemon leaves (12–15 cm) with ~1,000 *T. erytreae* fifth instar nymphs were cut and placed in evolutionary plastic cages (30 × 15 × 15 cm). Newly emerged adults (<12 hr old) were collected with a manual vacuum device and used in the experiments.

2.2 | Efficacy of commercial anti-insect meshes

Two experiments were carried out in a pesticide-free lemon orchard (cv. Fino) at ICIA. The first was carried out in spring (June 1–4) and the second in summer (August 1–4) 2018. Four commercial anti-insect meshes (Cotexa Alcalaina S.A.) were tested and compared to a muslin cloth, which was used as a positive control (Table 1). The experimental arena consisted of a cylindrical plastic tube (11.5 × 3 cm diameter) with both parts sealed hermetically with each corresponding

TABLE 1 Technical details of the commercial anti-insect meshes used to evaluate their efficacy as a method of exclusion against *Trioza erytreae* in citrus

Type of mesh	Threads (cm ²)	Pore size (mm ²)
Mosquito mesh 1	6 × 6	1.39 × 1.39
Mosquito mesh 2	6 × 9	1.39 × 0.83
Anti-thrip mesh 1	16 × 10	0.4 × 0.77
Anti-thrip mesh 2	20 × 10	0.27 × 0.77
Muslin fabric (control)	30 × 30	0.2 × 0.2

anti-insect mesh. For each experiment date and mesh, adult females and males were evaluated separately. In total, ten lemon trees were used as replicates in each experiment. Ten experimental arenas (five meshes \times two sexes) were placed randomly in different branches of each lemon tree. The experimental arenas were held \sim 20 cm inside the citrus tree canopy to prevent sunlight from affecting the psyllids.

To evaluate the efficacy of each commercial anti-insect mesh, 20 *T. erytrae* adults were separated by sex and introduced into each arena with one drop of honey spread onto the arena wall (Multi-flower honey, Apisol S.A.). The numbers of escaped and dead psyllids were checked daily. The mean abiotic conditions registered in both experiments were $21.3 \pm 1.3^\circ\text{C}$ and $73.5 \pm 2.6\%$ of RH and $21.6 \pm 1.9^\circ\text{C}$ and $77.3 \pm 2.2\%$ of RH for the first and second assay, respectively. It did not rain during the experiments.

2.3 | Survival of *T. erytrae* adults on fruit

The experimental arenas for the following assays consisted of a plastic cage ($14 \times 12 \times 6$ cm) with fine holes in the lid to provide ventilation. The fruit was fixed in the cage with plasticine (Plastilina Jovi[®] JOVI, S.A.). In each arena, ten newly emerged adults were introduced. Lemon and mandarin fruit used in the assays were collected

from a pesticide-free orchard in Realejos. All the assays were carried out in climate chambers located at ICIA.

We first determined whether the presence of honey, simulating other potential carbohydrate sources, could increase the survival of *T. erytrae* adults. This is because citrus rind can have rich carbohydrate sources such as juice from adjacent and broken fruits and/or honeydew excreted by hemipterans (Tena, Llácer, & Urbaneja, 2013). For this test, ten newly emerged adults were introduced to the arenas without fruit but with either water or a honey solution (75% vol/vol). Both diets were provided in wet cotton and were renewed daily. This assay was carried out at $13.5 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $85.4 \pm 10\%$ RH. Since honey did not affect the survival of *T. erytrae* adults, the following assay was conducted without adding honey.

We then carried out one assay with three treatments: (a) lemon fruit and (b) mandarin fruit (cv. clementine, *Citrus reticulata* Blanco) under winter conditions ($13.5 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$; $85.4 \pm 10\%$ RH and L14:D10 hr photoperiod) and, (c) lemon fruit under summer conditions ($23.5 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $65.4 \pm 10\%$ RH and L14:D10 hr photoperiod). These three treatments were used to compare the effect of the season (winter versus summer) and fruit (lemon versus mandarin under winter conditions). A total of ten replicates (one fruit per experimental arena) with ten newly emerged adults per replicate were carried out for each treatment.

FIGURE 1 Proportion (mean \pm SE) of *Trioza erytrae* female (grey) and male (white) escapees from the five insect meshes studied, 3 days after the onset of the assay during the first (a) and second (b) experiment under field conditions

2.4 | Data analysis

We used a generalized linear model (GLM) assuming a binomial distribution with the logit link function to analyse the proportion of females and males that escaped by the end of the assay (72 hr) with “anti-insect mesh” as the explanatory factor. The survival of *T. erytreae* on citrus fruit was analysed using Cox model survival analysis. Before the survival analysis, we confirmed that there were no differences between the replicates of each treatment with honey and water supply ($F_{1,9} = 2.89$; $p = .969$, and $F_{1,9} = 2.93$; $p = .967$, respectively), lemon fruit and mandarin fruit under winter conditions ($F_{1,9} = 12.14$; $p = .205$, and $F_{1,9} = 13.88$; $p = .126$, respectively) and lemon fruit under summer conditions ($F_{1,9} = 5.99$; $p = .740$). Coxph function was used to determine if there were differences among survival curves in *T. erytreae* to assess the effect of diet (honey versus water), citrus fruit (lemon versus mandarin) and abiotic conditions (lemon winter versus lemon summer conditions). The statistical software package “R” (<http://www.R-project.org>) was used for these analyses.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Efficacy of insect mesh

In both field experiments, no *T. erytreae* psyllids were able to escape from meshes with pore sizes of $0.4 \times 0.77 \text{ mm}^2$, $0.27 \times 0.77 \text{ mm}^2$ and $0.2 \times 0.2 \text{ mm}^2$ (control) at 72 hr after the onset of the assay (Figure 1).

The proportion of *T. erytreae* escapees from the anti-insect meshes was the highest from meshes with pore sizes of 1.39×1.39 and $1.39 \times 0.83 \text{ mm}^2$ during the first (females: $F_{4,49} = 77.74$; $p < .001$ and males: $F_{4,49} = 73.07$; $p < .001$) and second experiments (females: $F_{4,49} = 85.41$; $p < .001$ and males: $F_{4,49} = 77.98$; $p < .001$). All individuals were alive after 48 hr of the experiments in anti-insect meshes of $0.4 \times 0.77 \text{ mm}^2$, $0.27 \times 0.77 \text{ mm}^2$ and $0.2 \times 0.2 \text{ mm}^2$ (Figure 2).

3.2 | Survival of *T. erytreae* adults on citrus fruit

The presence of honey did not increase the survival of *T. erytreae* adults when compared to water (honey versus water: $F_{1,199} = 1.79$; $p = .074$) and adults lived a mean of 1.9 ± 0.1 days (max = 4, min = 1). When we compared the survival of the psyllid adults between winter and summer conditions in lemon fruit, adults lived significantly longer under winter (4.1 ± 0.3 days; max = 11, min = 1) than under summer conditions (1.1 ± 0.1 ; max = 3, min = 1) ($F_{1,199} = 9.94$; $p < .001$) (Figure 3). When we compared the survival of the psyllid adults between fruits under winter conditions, adults lived significantly longer on lemon than on mandarin (3.2 ± 0.1 max = 7, min = 1) ($F_{1,199} = 2.77$; $p = .006$).

4 | DISCUSSION

This study evaluated preventive methods to avoid the spread of *T. erytreae* in citrus areas where this psyllid is not present. Our results

FIGURE 2 Proportion (mean \pm SE) of females and males alive during the assay for each insect mesh studied during the first and second experiments under field conditions

FIGURE 3 Survival (mean \pm SE) of *Trioza erytreae* adults when they had access to (a) water or a honey solution, (b) mandarin or lemon at winter conditions, or lemon summer conditions

provide two important findings. First, there are two commercial anti-insect meshes reliable as a physical control to prevent the entrance of *T. erytreae* in citrus-growing nurseries. Second, the survival of this psyllid is possible on fruit, and it is higher on lemon fruit under winter conditions.

Prior to this work, two studies measured the thorax and wing size of *T. erytreae*, which are on average 0.54 mm and 0.97 mm for female psyllids, and 0.47 mm and 0.86 mm for males, respectively (Aidoo et al., 2019; Cocuzza et al., 2017). Despite these differences between sexes, our results showed that both meshes with pore sizes of $0.4 \times 0.77 \text{ mm}^2$ and $0.27 \times 0.77 \text{ mm}^2$ prevented the escape of females and males. Indeed, more than 75% of the psyllids were alive after 48 hr in the tubes covered by these meshes. Therefore, the adult psyllids did not die within the first hours of the experiment and had time to escape. For future assays, we would recommend finishing the experiment after 48 hr because the mortality had increased rapidly by 48 hr. These results should be used to design new citrus-growing nurseries and can also be used to grow adult citrus under protective meshes (like huge greenhouses) or even to develop young citrus trees under individual protective covers if HLB is detected in Europe, as is currently being done in Florida

(Qureshi, Stelinski, & Alfrez, 2019; Schumann, Singerman, Wright, & Ferrarezi, 2019).

Trioza erytreae adults could survive up to 11 days on unprocessed lemon fruit under winter conditions. The higher longevity of *T. erytreae* under winter conditions is in agreement with previous studies, which showed that this psyllid lives longer in cold and moist climates (Green & Catling, 1971). Our survival results also showed that *T. erytreae* adults feed on lemon and mandarin peel because they lived only 3 days when they did not have access to food. Although young leaves are the most attractive and nutritious organs for adults of *T. erytreae* (Moran, 1968), the psyllid might obtain some nutrients in citrus peels (Wang, Chuang, & Hsu, 2008). Overall, these results demonstrated that *T. erytreae* adults could survive for more than 10 days on unprocessed citrus fruit, and their movement could increase the risk of *T. erytreae* exponentially spreading, as occurred with *D. citri* in Florida in 2007. Individuals of *D. citri* were found alive in different citrus trucks during the transport of unprocessed oranges (Halbert et al., 2010). For this reason and to minimize the accidental introduction of *T. erytreae*, it is essential to consider all possible pathways of entry for the vector and adopt new quarantine methods.

The results showed in the present study can be used to improve contingency plans against *T. erytrae* worldwide, which should consider the use of anti-insect meshes in citrus nurseries located in recently invaded areas, and consider the problem of the movement of unprocessed citrus fruit through areas free of *T. erytrae*.

In our work, we have evaluated survival in two citrus cultivars: mandarins as a cultivar harvested in winter and lemons as a cultivar harvested throughout the year. It is known that *T. erytrae* behaves differently towards different members of the Rutaceae family, that is oviposition and larval development (Aubert, 1987). However, future research would be necessary to find out whether the survival of *T. erytrae* varies greatly in other citrus cultivars compared to those tested here, mandarin and lemon. In particular, it is urgent to investigate survival on oranges.

In conclusion, our research lays the groundwork to use anti-insect meshes to avoid/delay the entrance of *T. erytrae* in citrus areas currently free of this pest, especially in citrus-growing nurseries, and to produce citrus if the vector and disease invade the citrus-producing regions in mainland Europe. The adoption of preventive and rigorous quarantine measures is essential to avoid the spread of *T. erytrae*, especially by the transport of freshly harvested fruit from infested to uninfested areas. Further investigations are needed to determine which measures would best prevent the movement of *T. erytrae* on unprocessed citrus fruit. Here, we provide evidence that preventive measures should be adopted by growers, citrus nurseries and citrus producers that are present in susceptible citrus regions, such as the Mediterranean Basin, to avoid the spread of *T. erytrae* from infested citrus areas to areas without psyllid presence.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

All authors conceived research; PUB conducted experiments; EHS contributed material; PUB and AT analysed data and conducted statistical analyses; AT, AU, PUB and EHS wrote the manuscript; AT, AU, EHS secured funding; All authors read and approved the manuscript.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The authors of this article agree with the Data Accessibility Statement, and they confirm that if the manuscript is accepted, the data supporting the results will be archived in an appropriate public repository, and DOI data will be included at the end of the article.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section.

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